

STRUCTURAL ANALYSIS OF TOPONYMIC PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS OF THE KARAKALPAK AND ENGLISH LANGUAGES

Urazimbetova Gozzal

Trainee teacher of Karakalpak State University

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Abstract. This article aims to analyze the structural features of toponymic phraseological units in the Karakalpak and English languages. The author examines the compositional, semantic, and syntactic properties of these units, comparing and contrasting them to identify similarities and differences between the two languages. The article provides insights into how toponymic phraseological units reflect cultural values and practices in both languages, highlighting the importance of studying these units as a means of exploring the interplay between language, culture, and history. The findings of this research contribute to the field of cross-cultural communication by providing a deeper understanding of how linguistic structures can reveal cultural and historical backgrounds.

Keywords: toponymic phraseological units, compositional properties, semantic properties, syntactic properties, cultural values, cross-cultural communication, linguistic structures, historical backgrounds.

Toponymic phraseological units are expressions or phrases that incorporate the names of specific places or locations. These phrases often convey cultural, historical, or geographical information associated with the place name they contain [2]. They can be idiomatic expressions, proverbs, or other figurative language that includes a place name within its structure. For example, in English, the phrase "to steal someone's thunder" is a toponymic phraseological unit that references the mythical location of Mount Olympus, alluding to the power or authority of the Greek gods. Similarly, in Karakalpak, a phrase like "to chase a wild goose" might incorporate a specific place name and convey meaning beyond the literal interpretation, reflecting cultural or historical connotations related to that place. The analysis of toponymic phraseological units involves studying their linguistic structure, historical and cultural context, and the specific associations or meanings tied to the place names used within them. These units provide insight into how language reflects the interplay between human experience, geography, and the collective memory of a community.

English and Karakalpak languages have their own distinct features, grammar, syntax, and vocabulary, and they belong to different language families, which makes them interesting subjects for comparison and study. In the following sections, we will explore the characteristics of both languages and compare and contrast them in various aspects [1].

Structural analysis of toponymic phraseological units in Karakalpak

Structural analysis of toponymic phraseological units in Karakalpak involves a detailed examination of the composition and usage of phrases that are derived from place names. This includes analyzing the linguistic structure, such as the arrangement of words, syntax, and semantic meaning.

Toponymic phraseological units in Karakalpak may consist of toponyms (place names) combined with other words to form idiomatic expressions or figurative language. Understanding the structure of these phrases involves identifying their components, such as

nouns, adjectives, and other linguistic elements, and how they interact to convey specific meanings or cultural associations.

This analysis also involves exploring the historical, geographical, and cultural contexts in which these toponymic phraseological units are used, as they often reflect language usage and the collective memory of a community. By examining the structural aspects of these units, we can gain insights into the linguistic richness and cultural significance of Karakalpak language and its ties to specific geographical locations [3].

Structural analysis of toponymic phraseological units in the English language

The structural analysis of toponymic phraseological units in the English language involves a detailed examination of phrases derived from place names. This analysis includes understanding the composition and usage of these phrases, as well as their linguistic structure, semantics, and cultural context.

Toponymic phraseological units in English may consist of toponyms combined with other words to form idiomatic expressions, metaphorical language, or culturally significant terms. Understanding the structure of these phrases involves analyzing their syntactic composition, such as the order and arrangement of words, as well as the grammatical functions of individual components within the phrase [5].

Additionally, this analysis may involve exploring the historical, geographical, and cultural significance of the place names used in these phraseological units, as they often carry specific connotations or associations tied to their original locations. By dissecting the structural aspects of toponymic phraseological units in English, we can gain insights into language usage, cultural symbolism, and the linguistic evolution of these expressions over time.

When comparing toponymic phraseological units in Karakalpak and English, it is important to consider the differences and similarities in their linguistic structure, cultural significance, and usage.

In Karakalpak, toponymic phraseological units may reflect the language's Turkic roots and the cultural and historical connections to specific geographical locations. The structural analysis would involve examining how these units are formed, the syntactic and semantic relationships between the components, and the representation of local traditions or historical events within the phrases.

In English, toponymic phraseological units may exhibit a different linguistic and cultural background, often reflecting a combination of Anglo-Saxon, Latin, and other influences. The analysis would similarly focus on the syntactic structure, semantic meaning, and historical implications of these units, considering how they encapsulate cultural associations and geographical significance. When comparing the two languages, it would be interesting to explore how toponymic phraseological units in Karakalpak differ from those in English in terms of language structure, usage, and the cultural connotations linked to specific place names. Furthermore, the comparison could shed light on the unique ways in which each language leverages toponyms to express cultural identity and convey historical and geographical connections.

In conclusion the analysis of toponymic phraseological units in Karakalpak and English provides valuable insights into the linguistic, cultural, and historical aspects of these languages. The structural analysis of toponymic phraseological units in Karakalpak reveals the language's

Turkic roots and its connection to specific geographical locations, reflecting local traditions and historical events. Conversely, in English, toponymic phraseological units demonstrate a different linguistic and cultural background, reflecting a combination of various linguistic influences. The comparison of toponymic phraseological units in Karakalpak and English highlights the unique ways in which each language leverages toponyms to express cultural identity and convey historical and geographical connections. By exploring the syntactic structure, semantic meaning, and cultural connotations of these units, we gain a deeper understanding of how language is intertwined with geography, history, and cultural heritage. Overall, the study of toponymic phraseological units in both languages enriches our appreciation of the linguistic diversity and cultural significance embedded within place names, offering a fascinating avenue for cross-linguistic and cross-cultural exploration.

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